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Towards Privacy-Aware Data Federation Platforms: A User-Centric Design Approach

Dimitra Papatsaroucha¹[0000-0002-8894-617X], Konstantina Pityanou¹[0000-0002-9998-6759], Aris S. Lalos²[0000-0003-0511-9302], Ilias Politis²[0000-0002-1083-0345], and Evangelos K. Markakis¹[0000-0003-0959-598X]

¹ Hellenic Mediterranean University, Heraklion 71410, Greece

² Industrial Systems Institute, ATHENA Research Center 15125, Patras, Greece

Abstract. Data federation platforms play a vital role in the integration and exchange of data across different domains, facilitating collaboration and enabling informed decisions. User-centered design is crucial in the development of such platforms as it fosters user engagement throughout the entire development process, thus prioritizing the needs and requirements of users for creating a solution that is both easy to use and user-driven. For instance, within the realm of data federation platforms, end-users’ requirements may include assurances of privacy and the ability to maintain control over the primary and secondary use of their data. Nevertheless, there seems to be a lack of attention to identifying User-centred requirements in the development of such systems following a holistic approach. This paper presents a user-centered design methodology that incorporates User Experience (UX) Research with the aim to gather User-centred requirements for guiding the development of a privacy-aware data federation platform. The research primarily aims to establish clear definitions of Personas, User Stories, and User-centred requirements, through a thorough study including interviews, surveys, focus groups, technical implementation feedback, and use case scenario testing, to ensure that development is in line with user preferences. Key findings highlight the significant user demand for privacy-aware data federation platforms, with a focus on multidisciplinary data exchange and secondary use of data. This study underscores the significance of prioritizing user empowerment when creating data federation platforms that prioritize privacy and can serve the diverse requirements of users in various domains.

Keywords: data platform, data space, data federation, user-centric design, user requirements, user experience.

1 Introduction

Given the fast-paced changes in data collection, sharing, and usage, it is crucial to prioritize user-centric design in data spaces or data federation platforms that aim to enable multi-disciplinary primary and secondary use of data across multiple stakeholders

concurrently all the while maintain privacy. Prioritizing end-user needs and objectives during the development process is essential for building confidence, adhering to regulations, and protecting sensitive information. Users frequently demand guarantees of privacy and may wish to maintain control over the primary and secondary use¹ of their data. Integrating these factors into the creation of data spaces and privacy-aware data federation platforms not only improves user experience but also strengthens their integrity. Hence, the recognition of User-centred requirements is not only a procedural measure, but a fundamental element in developing data solutions that promote user empowerment.

User Experience (UX) is closely linked to technical products and encompasses its usability, design, and overall user experience. UX is related to Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) that focuses on the result of a user's interaction with a technological solution, product, or service. It takes into account all aspects of the product, from the aesthetic to the interactive and the context in which it is used. This assists in aligning the product with the user's specific needs and objectives [1]. Additionally, user-centric design incorporates users in all stages of a product's life cycle, prioritizing their needs and requirements, with the goal of creating a product that is user-driven and is easy to use. This involves performing UX Research that encompasses methods and tools such as interviews, surveys, focus groups, and other techniques to determine the requirements of users for the product [2]. The information collected is subsequently structured to create Personas, which are fictional representations of actual users [2], [3]. Additionally, User Stories are produced by identifying the needs and objectives of the Personas and refer to scenarios that depict Personas engaging in a specific task while also considering their behaviour and thoughts throughout the process. Following, Personas and User Stories are utilized to derive User-centred requirements [4]. User Stories encapsulate the objectives that a user aims to accomplish, whereas User-centred requirements delineate the product's features that revolve specifically around the users' demands.

UX research plays a crucial role in understanding and explaining the way consumers engage with data on privacy-aware data federation platforms. It encompasses a diverse array of tasks, including data input, collection, organization, and comprehension. Furthermore, users require access to interfaces and tools that facilitate data analysis, provide insights for decision-making, and enhance productivity. Nevertheless, other challenges arise, such as the requirement for specialized expertise, data organization, structural complexity, and a diverse range of data sources. Personas aid in identifying and specifying such obstacles and requirements, as well as offering understanding of the design and development process as they facilitate the creation of use case scenarios, i.e., descriptive narratives for the use of data federation platforms. Developers possess the capacity to identify potential constraints in tools utilized for data management and analysis, as well as privacy concerns that may emerge from the assessment, exploitation, primary and secondary use of data.

This paper outlines the approach and results of our study on gathering User-centered requirements for building data federation platforms that prioritize privacy. Our study, carried out in the context of developing such a platform, includes interviews, surveys,

¹ Using data for a different purpose than their primary purpose of use.

focus groups, and use case scenario testing. Using these techniques, Personas have been established, their User Stories have been determined, and User-centered requirements have been extracted, guiding the technical development of the platform. The goal of this paper is to assist in developing data solutions that promote user empowerment and also maintain privacy and integrity while sharing data across different domains and stakeholders.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: chapter 2 presents related work identified in the literature regarding user-centric design for the development of data federation platforms; chapter 3 describes the methodology followed in this study for defining Personas and User Stories, and extracting User-centred requirements; chapter 4 presents and discusses the results of the this study; and chapter 5 provides the concluding remarks of this paper.

2 Related Work

User-centered requirements define users' needs and expectations for a platform, which may vary based on its scope. However, in the context of data federation platforms, there's a notable deficiency in adhering to user-centered design principles, including the imperative for data privacy. For instance, [5] emphasizes transparent privacy policies and user consent but doesn't address data federation perspectives explicitly. Similarly, in health domains, [6] highlights declining trust in technology companies and the need for robust privacy measures but lacks insight into specific user concerns. [7] overlooks user-centric privacy perspectives, suggesting further research is needed to bridge this gap.

Furthermore, [8] focuses on user-centered design principles in health domains but doesn't detail the methodology for extracting user-centered requirements. Similarly, [9] aims to integrate User-Centered Design into a geovisualization platform but doesn't fully address users' holistic needs. In multidisciplinary data exchange, [10] stresses user-centered design, while [11] focuses solely on technological and organizational requirements, neglecting user-centric considerations. [12] evaluates an open data platform but overlooks user-centered requirements, highlighting a gap in prioritizing user needs alongside usability. Moreover, [13] provides a framework for user-centered interaction design patterns but overlooks explicit privacy requirements.

While existing research explores the identification of certain types of User-centred requirements for various platforms (e.g., privacy requirements), there is a notable absence of studies specifically addressing User-centred requirements for data federation platforms. These platforms, which involve the seamless integration and sharing of data across multiple sources, present unique challenges, and opportunities. Despite their increasing importance in data ecosystems, there is limited literature that focuses on understanding and defining the specific needs and preferences of users within the context of data federation platforms. By bridging this gap and prioritizing research efforts in this area, the aim is to ensure the development of user-centric platforms for privacy-aware data federation that effectively meet the diverse needs of their users across different domains and applications.

3 Methodology

The User-centred requirements engineering process described in this paper is employed for the development of a privacy-aware data federation platform that aims to enable the secure aggregation of multidisciplinary data sources, with a focus on maintaining privacy and data integrity. By employing a wide range of technologies, such as Homomorphic Encryption (HE) techniques and advanced ontologies, this platform aims to allow for secure access and analysis of data while also guaranteeing privacy, fairness, and adherence to European regulations. The platform aspires to facilitate complex queries, seamless Machine Learning (ML) processes – such as Federated Learning (FL) approaches for collaborative learning – and encourages the multi-disciplinary sharing of data, spanning domains such as energy, health, education, space, and automotive, nurturing a pan-European federated data ecosystem.

The UX Research methodology followed for defining the User-centred requirements for this privacy-aware data federation platform comprised two iterations and several steps to ensure that the developed solution will remain tailored to end-user needs. These iterations and steps are described in more detail in the sub-sections that follow. All the methods offered a different perspective of the end-users' requirements and constituted communication bridges between end-users and developers of the platform.

3.1 1st Iteration of User-centred Requirements Elicitation

The 1st iteration of User-centred requirements elicitation included three steps, namely: the conduct of one-to-one interviews with end-users, the development of a survey and the analysis of responses of end-users, and discussions with end-users distributed into focus groups through a workshop.

The one-to-one interviews were performed with a focus in identifying initial technical specifications for the platform and recognizing end-user needs from such a solution. Interviews have the benefit of getting close with the user by asking questions, extracting detailed information about their thoughts, feelings, and desires regarding the product. These interviews provided preliminary insight for User-centred requirements, mainly referring to data provision and secondary data use, and revealed an initial set of User Role groups.

Following, and based on the feedback gathered through the interviews, the Survey was developed by gathering a large pool of questions. Surveys have a structured format, and they can collect information from large groups of people, thus providing quantitative information regarding user requirements, in contrast with the qualitative type of information that interviews provide. The Survey developed and distributed to potential platform end-users aimed at delving deeper in goals and frustrations of end-users that the platform will eventually serve by determining the Personas based on the initial set of User Role groups, identifying and developing their User Stories, and extracting their User-centred requirements.

Personas, as a user-modelling technique, they contribute to product design of end-user products, based on real data gathered from interviews, demographics or information from surveys. Their creation includes an image or illustration, personal

characteristics and information, thoughts, description, goals, and needs. Personas succeed in representing real users and use case scenarios, identifying problems and User-centred requirements, giving the designers and developers the chance to empathize with them, understand their needs and come up with solutions to these desires and problems [2], [3]. In addition, User Stories are stories that relate to Personas and aim to picture the Persona while they are working or performing a task as well as their behaviour and thoughts regarding that context. This way, the developers may identify User-centred requirements while they highlight the requirements' priority stage [14]. The designers and developers relate to the fictional characters, understand and identify their needs, and therefore are able to come up with solutions and product aspects that ensure functionality and a pleasant experience [15].

The Survey included 11 sections with a total of 48 questions relating to, among others: the profile of the platform's end-user, including job role, age group, years of experience, and work routine; information about data use activities of the end-user (e.g., data entry, manipulation, collection, modification, querying, sharing, analysis, and data computations) and the amount of time spent on such activities; goals, potential benefits, and obstacles in sharing and accessing data for secondary use; expectations from the solution relating to foreseen benefits and requirements.

Finally, the Workshop was organized for getting together with potential end-users and stakeholders, where participants were distributed into focus-groups with the aim, among others, to discuss, validate, and enhance Personas and User-centred requirements. Focus groups are a gathering of approximately ten end-users that may answer questions or respond to a prototype, relate to specific enquires around why certain issues or challenges emerge, and allow for more open-ended and deeper discussions around specific contexts. Their thoughts and observations can lead to ideas and suggestions that will evolve the product and take the whole creativity process to the next level. Questions such as needs, challenges, and opportunities for having a privacy-aware data federation platform guided the collection of information and the cross-validation of User-centred requirements.

3.2 2nd Iteration of User-centred Requirements Elicitation

After the 1st iteration of User-centred requirements elicitation was finalized, the initial list of extracted User-centred requirements guided the initiation of technical implementation, leading to the development of a first proof-of-concept demonstrator of the platform. Furthermore, Use Case Demo Scenarios were defined for each one of the Personas, integrating various components of the platform. The PoC demonstrator was presented to potential end-users through workshops, whereas Use Case Demo Scenarios were thoroughly studied and extensively tested. Both processes were adopted in order to gather additional feedback and identify any additional Personas and User-centred requirements that eluded the 1st iteration.

4 Results

During the 1st iteration of User-centred requirements elicitation, five (5) interviews were conducted, which provided preliminary insight into the needs and objectives of potential end-users and revealed certain User Role groups, namely Researcher (including Senior Researcher, Associate Researcher), Manager (including Project Manager, Technical Manager) and General Employee (including Data Scientist/Analyst, Software Developer, AI/ML Engineer/Developer).

Following, the distribution of the Survey that was developed led to gathering thirty-five (35) responses. **Fig. 1** presented below summarizes the findings for a subset of these questions.

Fig. 1. Survey Results Analysis

The analysis of data from **Fig. 1** (A, B, C) reveals insightful patterns across domains and participant demographics. The Automotive domain shows significant representation in Senior Researcher and Technical Manager roles, with Healthcare and Energy domains also exhibiting substantial involvement. Conversely, the Multi-disciplinary domain displays minimal representation. Healthcare stands out for age diversity, while Automotive has more participants in younger age groups. Most participants across all domains possess 3-15 years of experience, although Automotive features a notable number with over 15 years.

Data from **Fig. 1** (D, E, F, G) provides insight on various data usage activities and time spent, obstacles encountered, and types of computations across domains. Healthcare shows extensive involvement across tasks, while Automotive focuses on data analysis. Participants from Automotive predominantly invest 2-4 hours in data activities, while Healthcare participants display diverse time allocations. Data input and manipulation provide challenges for the Automotive, Energy, and Space domains. Automotive engages mostly in mathematical operations and data visualization, with notable involvement in machine learning.

Responses from **Fig. 1** (H) highlight varied motivations for utilizing a privacy-aware data federation platform across domains, with Automotive and Healthcare showing interest in machine learning and diversity. The Energy domain expresses interest in accessing annotated datasets, while Healthcare and Space domains show interest in data exchange. Education and Energy domains demonstrate some interest in synergies among pillars.

The analysis of the survey results led to the identification of the initial set of platform Personas, namely: Data Provider, Consumer, and Developer. For these Personas a total of 140 User Stories were developed based on their goals, frustrations, and ambitions for privacy preserving data computations as well as secondary use of data. In order to

formulate the User Stories of the platform Personas, the following template was used: “As a <User Persona> I want to <Goal> so that <Benefit>”.

Following, each User Story produced one or more User-centred requirements, while in other cases more than one Use Stories were combined to produce a single User-centred requirement. After gathering all the User-centred requirements, any duplicate records were removed or merged, resulting in an initial set of 119 User-centred requirements. Furthermore, the Workshop that was held during this 1st iteration led to cross-validation of the identified Personas, User Stories, and User-centred requirements as well as to their enhancement. An additional Persona was identified, namely the Model Provider, while User Stories and User-centred requirements were also enhanced as their number was increased to 160 and 121, respectively.

During the 2nd iteration of User-centred requirements elicitation, technical implementation progress, Use Case Demo Scenario testing, and feedback gathered for the first PoC demonstrator of the platform revealed that a partition of the Consumer Persona into Data Consumers and Model Consumers was required for the sake of precision. However, this distinction and segmentation did not affect the entirety of the User Stories and User-centred requirements. This is because the objectives and frustrations of both Data and Model Consumers were already incorporated into the User Stories of the Consumer Persona and the User-centred requirements that were derived from them. Furthermore, there was a discovery of an additional Persona defined as the FL Prosumer Persona, which combines the roles of Model Provider and Model Consumer with a particular focus on Federated Learning scenarios; thus, this Persona can simultaneously function as a Provider and a Consumer of AI Models. This Persona was meticulously examined in relation to the automotive data domain. The finalized lists of User Stories and User-centred requirements were also formulated after the completion of the 2nd iteration of User-centred requirements elicitation, concluding in a set of 165 User Stories and 126 User-centred requirements, respectively. Each User-centred requirement was tagged with a specific priority based on the respective User story from which it was derived, following the MoSCoW requirement prioritization method: Must Have (Mandatory Requirements), Should Have (Desirable Requirements), Could Have (Optional Requirements), Won’t Have (Future Enhancement Requirements)².

Fig. 2 below summarizes the methodology that was followed for the elicitation of User-centred requirements alongside the results (i.e., Personas, User Stories, User-centred requirements) that were produced in each step .

Fig. 2. Methodology and Results

After the completion of both iterations, the initial set of Personas was finalized, as illustrated in **Fig. 3** below, resulting in a total of six (6) Personas for the privacy-aware data federation platform, as follows:

² <https://www.agilebusiness.org/dsdm-project-framework/moscow-prioritisation.html>

- Data Provider, who aims to register their dataset to the platform while retaining total control over them.
- Data Consumer, who aims to search for datasets registered to the platform Data Providers and/or perform lightweight computations over them in the encrypted domain.
- Model Provider, who aims to register their AI models to the platform.
- FL Prosumer, who acts as both a Model Provider and Model Consumer and aims to participate in FL rounds and offer to the platform the homomorphically encrypted parameters of their locally trained models for HE-enabled aggregation/fusion with the goal of contributing to the extraction of more powerful Global AI Models which are subsequently stored in the platform.
- Model Consumer, who aims to explore and use Global AI Models stored in the platform by requesting to download and use them with their own local data.
- Developer, who aims to use exposed functionalities of the platform without having to develop them from scratch.

Fig. 3. Personas

Fig. 4 below shows an example of one of the Personas that was developed, particularly for the automotive domain.

Jim Cross
 Domain: Automotive
 Age group: 50-60 years
 Occupation: Technical Manager
 Years of experience: 15+ years
 Daily data usage: 2-4 hours
 TRUSTEE Role: Data Provider

"I want to upload data easier and without manual effort"

Goals

- Data exchange with space and other domains
- Aggregate data from multiple vendors
- Collaboration with various domains, such as energy, transportation, climate, weather, forecasting, and civil engineering
- Data synchronization while maintaining data integrity
- Data compression
- Share annotated non-personal data relating to sensory inputs, automotive simulators, and vehicles

Frustrations

- "It frustrates me that data annotation is of high demand, time-consuming, and requires expertise and manual effort."
- "It frustrates me that EPR and data privacy issues restrict data sharing"

Jim is a Technical Manager in the automotive domain mainly involved in software testing, integration, and review on data acquired by cameras, lidars, radars, and usrs. Through his domain, he can provide data related to Federated Learning, Output or Private Grounds captured video (fictitious), as well as Key Performance Indicators. Moreover, he can share data relating to photo-realistic artificially generated scenes, alphas outputs, Key Performance Indicators, evaluation protocols, and validation benchmarks.

Fig. 4. Data Provider Persona

This Persona produced several User stories that described its goals and frustrations as a Data Provider. One of these User stories describes how Jim wants to be certain about the way his data are used, for which he has provided platform with access, so that he

can terminate the procedure if he identifies any violations of his interests. This User Story was formulated as follows, using the template reported above:

As a < *Technical Manager in the automotive domain* > **I want to** < *be certain I will get informed regarding the way that my data are used (accessed, processed, utilized) for the training of any AI model* > **so that** < *I am always aware of how my data are used and I can terminate the procedure if I identify any violation of my interests.* >

Eventually, this User Story produced 2 User-centred requirements, that were identified as Mandatory and Desirable, respectively, as follows:

- “The user must always be aware of how their data are used and they must be able to terminate the procedure if any violation of their interests may happen”.
- “The user should get informed regarding the way that their data are used (accessed, processed, utilized) for the training of any model)”.

5 Conclusion

This paper presented a thorough method for gathering User-centered requirements for a data federation platform that prioritizes privacy. The method involved conducting interviews, surveys, engaging with focus-groups through workshops, and incorporating feedback stemming from technical implementation progress and use case scenario testing in iterative cycles to connect with end-users. This assisted in defining Personas, User Stories, and User-centered Requirements, which, as a result, guide the development of the solution, to ensure that the platform and stakeholders' expectations remain in perfect harmony.

It is important to highlight that the analysis of the results of the Survey revealed that users have a significant interest in such a platform, emphasizing security and identity management while Data Providers prioritized the need to retain total control over the data that they share through such a platform. In addition, the integration of HE with FL has emerged as a convincing approach for ensuring privacy. Focal points were also the sharing of data across different domains as well as the secondary use of data.

In particular, within domains such as Automotive and Healthcare, it was observed that certain factors, such as the accuracy of data and the need for real-time processing, were given special attention. The presence of many data sources posed difficulties, however, the implementation of approaches such as multi-disciplinary data sharing was recognized as a potential solution to overcome these obstacles.

Moving forward, these findings will further guide the development of the platform to ensure it continues to meet the changing demands of users. The primary focus is on empowering users, preserving privacy, and maintaining data integrity by providing a framework that enables smooth data flow and promotes trust and collaboration among different domains and stakeholders.

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